

BB-2208
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

ASSIGNMENT
Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad

Harvard Model

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Abstract

Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad is a private limited company and only one of the few companies here in Brunei that specialized in shrimp farming, the company joined aquaculture in 1994 and fully operational in 1995. The issue that the company faced was they were unable to control and contain the White Spot Virus (WSV) that hit the company in 2010, which caused a major loss for the company's finances and almost caused the company to go bankrupt. The reason for this issue is that the company has little to none Human Resource (HR) practice which leads to an outcome that causes a negative impact to the company because the workers are unable to prevent the pandemic to spread that led to losses of three tonnes of shrimps per pond from all the 22 ponds. To understand this issue by using the Harvard Model will be applied and to explain the issue caused and provide solutions to avoid similar cases. There are two solutions to solve the company's issue, first is to design and implement an HR strategy solution which focuses on the manager of the company to create and practice HR within the company. The second is to train and develop workers' solutions which focus on the worker to gain new skills and knowledge that benefits the company.

Problem Statement

To start, what is Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad and what do they do? According to the book *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei* by Musa et al. (2020), Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad is a private limited company and only one of the few companies here in Brunei that specialized in shrimp farming, the company joined aquaculture in 1994 and fully operational in 1995. The company is currently being managed by Ampuan Ammilee Farahiyah after her late father Ampuan Haji Mohamad bin Ampuan Haji Yusof. The mission of the company is to supply quality organic rostris blue shrimp without the use of pesticides and antibiotics while promising a disease-free shrimp. While the vision of the company to be the number one leading shrimp farm in Brunei and be a globally recognized enterprise

After Ampuan Ammilee Farahiyah took control of the company faced its first major problem, where a pandemic hit the company's shrimp farm in 2010 that led the company to deconstruct all of the 22 ponds and lose 3 tonnes of shrimps to prevent the spread of WSV. This caused the company to rebuild from scratch after the incident that cost a major financial loss to the company and almost bankrupt them. From the information from the book by Musa et al. (2020), the company was not prepared in the cases of any pandemic outbreaks on the company because they have no strategies and procedures to handle the outbreaks to prevent losses on the company. It was after the WSV incident that Ampuan Ammilee Farahiyah has taken several measurements to prevent another catastrophe happen to the company again, these measurements are to install various security protocols which include staff training, chlorine baths, quarantine units, and educating herself with the help from Fisheries Department on various shrimp diseases. All of these measurements are to ensure the protection of the shrimp farm and to prevent any future outbreak.

Case Analysis

As mentioned in the abstract, Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad has little to none HR practices that cause a severe financial loss when hit by the WSV pandemic, by the use of The Harvard Model to explain further on how to solve the issue. The figure below is the illustration of the Harvard Model, the model starts on the far left with the Stakeholder interest (stakeholders, management, employee groups, government, community, and unions), where the interests are to define the HR policies and at the same time Situational factors (workforce characteristics, business strategy and conditions, management philosophy, labor market, unions, task technology, laws, and societal values) influence these interest (Harvard Framework for HRM, n.d.). Stakeholder interest and Situational factors work together hand-to-hand to influence the HRM policies choices, it affects the activities of the organization which include employee influence, human resource flow, reward systems and work systems. If done correctly the HR policy will have a positive HR outcome (commitment, competence, congruence and cost-effectiveness). The HR outcomes leads to Long-term consequences, specifically on individual wellbeing, organizational effectiveness, and societal wellbeing. The Long-term consequences are important in the Harvard model as it shows that a business HR policy is effective or not, if it is effective it will go back to the beginning and continue to use the same HR policy or improve it to increase the Long-term consequences. If the policy is not effective then both the Stakeholder interest and Situational factors will learn from the problems and from that create a new HR policy to solve the problems (Boselie, 2015).

The Harvard Model (Boselie, 2015)

To apply the Harvard Model to the Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad, we know that the issue here is that the company was unprepared when the WSV was hit in 2010 that caused severe losses. Based on the model and starting from the left, we know that both the Stakeholder interest and Situational factors have no interest and influence on HR policy before the incident, because of these there are no HR policy choices which resulted in the workers unable to control and contain the WSV because they have no set of skills and knowledge to prevent the spread of the outbreak. The outcomes of the uncontained WSV that the company has to deconstruct all the 22 shrimp ponds they had and each pond has three tonnes of shrimp needed to be disposed of. The loss of the shrimp farm affected the company's sales figures, as they needed to stop the production and sales of shrimps until the pandemic was cleared. As for the Long-term consequences, the company has a major financial loss that nearly bankrupted the company and they have to rebuild the shrimp farm from scratch.

Alternative Solutions

To solve the issue faced by the Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad, it must create HR strategies and procedures to prevent the WSV incident to ever happen again, the solution is related to the use of the Harvard Model and its six components that is the stakeholder interests, situational factors, HR policy choices, HR outcomes, and long-term consequences.

The first solution is to train and develop workers, this HR policy is focused on the workers of Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad. This solution is to train and develop workers, so they can gain new sets of skills, knowledge of shrimp-based pandemic, and experiences on how to effectively handle a pandemic. The reason for this solution is so the workers are prepared if any cases of pandemic outbreak hit the shrimp farm and to prevent the total losses of all its shrimp ponds, similar to the case of the WSV incident. From the Harvard Model, the HR policy choice is to train and develop workers by giving them skills, knowledge, and experience to prevent the outbreak of any pandemic. The HR outcomes are that workers are now more skilled, knowledgeable, and experienced, which benefits the long-term consequences as they are now able to control and contain any shrimp-based diseases and it also boosts the worker's performance in producing quality shrimps that bring positive impacts on the company such as increase on sales and reputation.

Training and development of workers may bring benefits to the Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad but it also has its drawbacks. One of the drawbacks is that training and development cost time and money, from the book (Musa et al., 2020) the company had to deconstruct all of its shrimp ponds and this is important information because without the shrimp farm the company is unable to produce shrimps and sell shrimps for revenue. With no revenue inflow the company was almost gone bankrupt when it focused on rebuilding itself from scratch, training and development cost money and the company did not have enough financial to spend on training and development but instead rebuilt. Only after the company is

financially stable then it can start training and developing workers. As for time, how long does it take for the company to be financially stable to afford the training and development and how long are the training and development. The cost of time is important as after the WSV incident, the company had to spend much of its time to rebuild and to recover its financial losses. Another drawback is training and development of workers may not bring benefits to the company because the training and development may not be personalized for specific roles or skills (Andriotis, 2019). The training and development may not be relevant to some workers and this will lead to a lower performance that can bring negative impact to the company as workers can not apply the skill, knowledge, and experience that are related to their jobs.

The second solution is to design and implement an HR strategy, an article by Luenendonk (2019) explained the step by step on how Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad design and implement its HR strategy. The first step is to define the company vision, Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad already has its mission and vision. The mission of the company is to supply quality organic rostris blue shrimp without the use of pesticides and antibiotics while promising a disease-free shrimp, while the vision of the company to be the number one leading shrimp farm in Brunei and be a globally recognized enterprise. These missions and vision give guidance to HR to achieve the goals of the company. After setting the mission and vision for the company the next step is to establish the HR department's role, this is where the HR department develops an effective HR strategy by understanding a specific task for the HR to handle example recruiting, training, payroll, and employees' benefits (Luenendonk, 2019). The next step is to develop a company overview, this is where the company is evaluated to observe the current company performance and provide a means to reach the company goals. In the case of Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad after evaluating the company after the WSV incident, HR needs to provide a strategy for the company to achieve its goals. In the next step, HR must investigate the company's needs by developing an effective HR strategy and seeking out human resources such as recruiting workers for the workforce. Next is to evaluate HR processes as the HR strategy is put in place, this is so the HR department is able to change and redesign the HR strategy that is best suited by the company. After developing and adjusting the HR strategy it is finally to implement the HR strategy into the company and evaluate the success of the HR strategy. If the HR strategy is successful it can have a positive impact on the company and if it fails the company will recreate a new HR strategy that uses the lesson learned from the failed strategy to find a new solution.

Similar to the previous solution, design and implement an HR strategy also has its drawbacks. Also similar to the previous solution it takes time and money to come up with an HR strategy and this process is not a one-time strategy because different issues may arise causing the HR to adapt to the new issues, this involves more time and money that the company may lack. Another problem is that the management changes may bring a negative impact on the company (Staffing, 2019) because of the changes in the management of the company, employees may have a difficult time to adapt to these new changes and can cause a reduction in performance and morale during the effect of management changes. Another one

from the book itself, the company divesting itself from key players so the company is able to make changes to their policies for the benefit of the company (Musa et al., 2020).

Recommendations

Both solutions are best suited for the company, designing and implementing an HR strategy and training and development of workers. The problem that needs to be taken into account is how much time and money the company is willing to forgo because designing and implementing an HR strategy cost more than training and development of workers. Designing and implementing an HR strategy has a greater effect on the company as it also has training and development of workers in its solution and for that, it is recommended that the company use the designing and implementing an HR strategy solution but only if the company is willing to spend more resources on time and money.

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